

DESIGNING INTERACTIONS BY DESIGNING BUSINESS MODELS

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ABSTRACT

The global economic crisis is pushing forwards thoughts and conjectures about productive models, their logics and features. In particular business model generation is emerging as a strategic issue to be addressed as many contributions from managerial and business sciences are pointing out (Amit, Zott, 2001; Teece, 2010).

Also design research, especially, the integrated design thinking framework (Brown, 2008; Martin, 2009) the area that relies on designers "tool box" are progressively addressing their contribution towards the generation of "value innovation" and its related business models (Kim, Mauborgne, 2005; Ostervalder, Pigneur, 2008).

In the current hybrid and networked economy a multiplicity of business models is prevailing that is making available different values that rely on diverse models of interactions between producers and consumers.

By exploiting a case based qualitative analysis the paper investigates the relations between models of interactions designed to support the producers-users communication, and the underlined business models.

Keywords: business models design, models of interaction

INTRODUCTION¹

During last years the attention on business models, and their innovation, raised up.

A growing number of academic contributions, as well as series of practitioners-based articles discuss business models as one of the top-of-mind concerns

¹ This paper represents a joint effort from both authors. Nevertheless Cabirio Cautela directly edited sessions 1, 2.1, 3 (all sub-sessions); Francesca Rizzo directly edited sessions 2.2, 4 and 5.

of executives and managers as also recently underlined by The Economist (The Economist Intelligent Unit - Business 2010 - Embracing the challenge of change).

Different driving factors can be individualized at the basis of this growing relevance. Among them the knowledge economy, the growth of Internet and e-commerce, the outsourcing and offshoring of many business activities, and the restructuring of financial services industry pushed companies to rethink and, in some cases, re-design their architecture values and primarily their business models (Johnson, Christensen, Kagermann, 2008; Teece, 2009).

There are different research streams and also different ways to assume and make operable business models. Some contributions, describing common features among different business models, suggest taxonomies and "archetypes" (Timmers, 1998; Rappa, 2001; Weil, Vitale, 2001), others try to identify business models "building blocks" and their relationship in order to provide operative templates to analyze and identify innovative business models (Baden Fuller, Morgan, 2010; Ostervalder, 2005, 2010; Johnson, Christensen, Kagermann, 2008), thirdly other scholars analyze the technological innovations, their failures and successes in relation to the adopted business models (Chesbrough, Rosenbloom, 2002; Teece, 2009; Tripsas, Gavetti, 2000).

Nevertheless, often the concept of business model remains ambiguous and "arcane" (Magretta, 2002). Further more most contributions assume an afterword and isolating perspective that lacks to identify the generative logics under the business model concept and the correspondent operative levers with which they are closely tied.

The paper, rooting business models according to one literature widespread framework, aims to clarify the

relation between them and the interaction models involving customers in the value creation process. Starting from the hypothesis that companies use interfaces and other operative levers to implement and execute their business models, this contribution suggests a framework that tries to link the company touch points system to a business model and provides some guidelines and design principles for interaction design practitioners - going beyond the dominant principles of user driven design that mainly consist in offering a wow experience or an optimal flow of interaction to the customers.

The paper on the basis on a in-depth qualitative survey on international emblematic case-studies, provides some evidence and results to strengthen the hypothesis underlined in the proposed framework: the business model drive the model of interaction between clients and companies and discusses a possible set of interaction design guidelines.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

In this session we present literature analysis about business and interaction models into two different sub-sessions in that way making evident that both domain of investigation have never been putted close to each other and that a joint literature does not exist (meaning an understanding of the relation between the two components have not yet been material of research and analysis).

SHORT THEORETICAL BACKGROUND ABOUT BUSINESS MODEL

Although literature on business model is growing quickly and reporting different perspectives and framings, yet there is no a common accepted definition of business model and a widespread manner to investigate it. Managerial literature offers different interpretations according with four main streams. The first one (Timmers, 1998; Tapscott, Lowy, Ticoll, 2000; Applegate 2001; Ostervalder, 2004; Mahadevan, 2000), recognizing similarities and differences among business models, is oriented to define typologies and constitutive components, i.e. the building blocks. This cluster is mainly based on e-business models as the internet economy triggered new value creation logics associated to the emergence of innovative business models.

The second stream, more philosophical, investigates the theoretical roots of business models connecting these with classical managerial concepts as strategy, competitive advantage, firm performance (Seddon, Lewis 2003; Zott, Amit, 2008; Teece, 2009).

According to these studies business models substantially differs with the concepts of strategy because the former explains the business logic and the value architecture - " which value delivers to the customer and how converts payments into profits" (Amit, Zott, 2001) - the latter matters with positioning and competition (Porter, 1990).

The third stream deals with the relation among innovation, technology management and business models (Chesbrough, Rosenbloom, 2002; Teece, 2009; Markides, 2006). According to this, technology has not "intrinsic value" so that management has to define the "most appropriate regime" to capture value and profiting by technological innovations. The last strand treats business models beyond their functional value (as mechanism to create and capture value) - as "stories, that explain how the enterprise works" (Magretta, 2002) or as "narratives" relying on linguistic techniques including the mobilization of fantasy scenarios, cultural myths appealing to archetypical figures and literary tropes as metaphors (Perkmann, Spicer, 2010).

In order to clarify the relation between business models and interaction models the contribution assumes business models according to two main operative and meaningful concepts emerging from literature:

- the first is characterized by a functional perspective according to which "business model depicts the content, structure, and governance of transactions designed so as to create value through the exploitation of business opportunities" (Amit, Zott, 2001);
- the second is oriented by a semiotic perspective according to which business models are "performative representations", specifically narratives used to entice users through the construction of acceptable and social meanings (Perkmann, Spicer, 2010).

Innovation in business model, therefore, can be assumed as variations, relative to the industry where company operates, of (Amit, Zott, 2001):

- transaction content, intended as goods or information that are being exchanged, and to the resources and capabilities that are required to enable the exchange;
- transaction structure, intended as “the parties that participate in the exchange and the ways in which these parties are linked”;
- transaction governance, intended as “the ways in which flows of information, resources, and goods are controlled by the relevant parties”.

According to these innovation options authors have identified four main innovation sources for business models (see figure1):

Figure 1 - Sources of Value creation in Business Model -
Adaptation from Amit, Zott (2001)

- novelty, as the introduction on the market of new transaction contents, structure or the inclusion of new participants within exchange;
- efficiency, as the achieving of scale economies, the minimization of search costs and selection range;
- lock-in, as the creation of high switching costs or positive network externalities that retain customers to the company offerings;
- complementarities, as bundling and cross-selling operations between products and services, between on-line and off-line assets, between technologies.

On the other hand, according to the semiotics layer, a business model can innovate through the creation of a new story, a new narrative that creates new representations and meanings by the introduction of new actors, the change of the events sequence, the depiction of fantastic and imaginary worlds.

Related to the two main layers of innovations - the functional and the semiotic one - touch points and interactions enabled by companies cannot be considered as neutral.

Interfaces enabling interaction models make business models working and operative. Without the real and effective interaction happening between user and companies by the means of their touch points business models would remain conceptual abstraction in the executive minds.

SHORT THEORETICAL BACKGROUND ABOUT INTERACTION MODELS

The dominant literature about interaction models is rooted in the user studies and Human Computer Interaction. In particular within the framework of this contribution it seems particularly relevant HCI (Preece, Rogers, Sharps, 2011) literature devoted to study models of interaction with information system. Information systems are all of the platforms developed to support information exchanges among different stakeholders by exploiting different channels and touch points. In this context we refer to the idea of information system as the platform (and all the correspondent channels and tools) that mediate the communication between a company and its customers.

The principal activity performed by users in interacting with an information system is an information seeking task, a process driven by an information problem. Examples of typical information problems (ISs) are: monitoring a current state or situation, getting information to make a decision, looking for an accommodation, booking a flight, finding a plumber to keeping informed about a business competitor, satisfying a curiosity, writing a publishable article, or investigating a new field. Addressing an information problem must be initiated with a conscious activity to reach an object or goal. A person engaged in seeking a solution to an information problem has one or more than one goal

in mind, and uses digital technologies as a supporting tool. Although the goals of an information access process (IAP) differ depending on the characteristics of the users, and the context and nature of the information problem, most ISs have been developed according to the findings of normative theories about human information processing and problem solving (Marti, 1999).

Current literature on models of interaction with information distinguishes among:

- basic models interaction;
- advanced models of interaction.

About the basic model of interaction Shneiderman noted in 1992 that the interaction style of the process of information access, navigation, use and manipulation can be described in terms of query specification, information receipt, examination of retrieval results, and then either stopping or reformulating the query and trying the process many times until a fitting result set is obtained.

While useful for describing the basics this simple interaction model contains an underlined assumption that the user's needs are static, and that the interaction process mainly consists of successively refining a set of actions until when users is satisfied with his/her need.

For this reason, as reported by Spink and Saracevic (1998) and Chesni and Rizzo (2000) many reviews of the subject literature focus on the iterative, uncertain and unpredictable nature of these tasks. According to this idea, an individual interact with an IS in order to remedy a personal knowledge lack. Practically, a user in this model is concerned with a problem, but the problem itself and the information needed to solve the problem are not clearly understood. The user must go through a process of clarification by continuously shift his / her attention on the content or the interaction. In this context, an IS should support iterative and interactive communication flow with the user. This advanced model characterizes how a user perceived needs change during the interaction process as a consequence of retrieved results feedback. In 1989, Bates developed the "berrypicking" model of information seeking based on two main observations. The first is that, as a result of reading

and learning from the information encountered throughout the search process, the users' information needs and their queries continually shift. From these literature review it is possible to individualized three general models of interaction:

- a task based model of interaction represented from the basic model of information seeking. This model is characterized for a high level of efficiency and usability. It is driven by the design principles that less is more. People need to solve their problem performing few and precise steps that can lead them to the satisfaction of a precise need.
- A search based model of interaction represented by the advanced models of interaction. Being in condition that can be defined as lack of knowledge means that people are "ready" to spend their resources to search about something that can be in their interest but they really don't know yet. This interaction model and the its correspondent interfaces need to be designed in order to present all of the correlated information that is possible to offer to the end users not only to satisfied their expressed needs (user centred view) but also to support them to link new things and have new experiences on related contents. Designers here are required to build and figure out possible new path of offerings and path of navigations and clustering to expect by end users.
- A discovering model of interaction. It aims always a model based on a lack of knowledge and experience not necessarily related to a specific content. This meaning that people continuously re-structure their needs depending on the interactive experience that they can live when they interact with a company. Design competences and knowledge are here applied to envisioning and design new possible users experiences.

WORKING HYPOTHESIS DERIVED FROM LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Despite the fact that business model concepts can be considered as the longa manus of the interaction models implemented by a company there is a strong lack of studies about the relation between the two.

Aim of the present contribution is to provide an answer to the following interdependent research questions:

- which are the functional main features of the interaction patterns related to different kinds of innovative business models?
- Which kind of performative representations and narratives these interactions enable?

BUSINESS MODEL THAT SHAPES INTERACTION PATTERNS: A CASE STUDY ANALYSIS

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To answer to the above hypothesis we applied a methodology based on a qualitative in-depth survey focused on indirect sources with the aim to analyze the relation between business models and interaction patterns in six successful and internationally recognized case-studies.

The choice of the case-studies has been driven by the following criteria:

- cases operating in different productive sectors;
- cases extensively recognized by literature and management press as representative for business model innovation;
- cases where digital interfaces (especially web based) and interaction patterns are "at the core" of their business models and value creation processes.

The criteria list above would ensure a wide accessibility to a large amount of data and information. Through public documents (balance sheet), literature articles and widespread press² it

² Companies Business models have been studied through different sources. In particular some are scientific literature articles: Timmers P., Business Models for electronic markets, *Electronic Markets*, 1998; Mahadevan B., Business models for Internet-based e-commerce: An anatomy, *California management review*, 2000 ; Torbay M.D., Osterwalder A., Pigneur Y., E-business model design, classification, and measurements, *Thunderbird*, Volume 44, Issue 1, 2002; Magretta J., Why business models matter, *Harvard Business Review*, 2001; others are official company sheet Amazon Annual Report 2010; Letter to Shareholder 2010 available at: <http://phx.corporate-ir.net/phoenix.zhtml?c=97664&p=irol-reportsAnnual>; e-

has been possible to identify the companies business model sources according to the Amit and Zott's previous framework.

The identification of the sources of business model has been also supported exploiting corporate communication. In different cases, in fact the company pay-off and other promotional services have strongly helped to confirm the business logics and the related source of value.

The analysis of the enabled models of interaction, has been, instead, conducted by a panel of seven senior interaction specialists and three semiotic scholars.

The former analyzed the functional dimension of the web based interactions identifying the main features of the interaction patterns; the latter conducted the semiotics analysis searching for the promoted performative representation and narrative structure. The analysis has been run through two main steps:

- first, experts browsed companies web sites simulating a purchase/use experience;
- second, they reported about their experience mainly through descriptive key-words and metaphors.

In this contribution only short abstracts for each case-study will be provided.

THE CASES ANALYSIS

The analysis has been conducted on the following case-studies:

- Priceline - a search engine for flights and other touristic services;
- Intuit, an accounting and tax planning software provider for small business and accountants;

Business and Supply Chain Integration, Hau L. Lee and Seungjin Whang, *International Series in Operations Research & Management Science*, 2004, Volume 62, Part 2, 123-138; others are document download from internationally acknowledged debated blogs as: The Problem with Groupon's Business Models, *Harvard Business Review Blog* Mc Grath R., <http://blogs.hbr.org/hbr/mcgrath/2011/07/the-problem-with-groupons-busi.html>

- Apple I-Tunes - the digital music portal to download songs, audio-books and videos connected to the I-Pod device;
- Facebook, the social media platform to connect with friends;
- Groupon, the company featuring a daily deal on entertainment and free time;
- Amazon, the diversified multi-items digital store.

For each case the analysis provided:

- the business model sources reconstruction, according to the Amit-Zott's model;
- the interaction model features identifying the emerging and relevant characteristics grasped during the interaction experience with companies interfaces;
- the performed representation interpretation, showing the core messages and meanings of the promoted texts and narratives.

Below case-studies are described according to these three domains.

PRICELINE: SEARCHING THE BEST TRAVEL DEAL

Priceline offers opportunities to "shop for discount travel", as claimed in the main tool bar of the website. Priceline business model is strongly based on the efficiency source. The company acts as a meta-player, through a touristic service search engine, offering the cheapest solutions and last minute promotions. Value is delivered to the user in the form of money saving with respect to alternative offerings; while is captured by the company and turned in profits through out the percentage fee charged on every single deal.

How this efficiency based business model is expressed through the interaction model it enables? The interaction model is based on simplicity, speed and the minimization of searching costs. Input data required are reduced to the minimum and during the query a sort "negotiator" appears promising he will search for the cheapest offering.

By using the functionality "name your own price" the user can make a bid waiting to receive the final deal that Priceline assumes in charge.

If the interaction model features are functionally aligned with the business model sources the

performative representation changes the traditional representation logic used for the touristic sector, both in virtual and real market. Currently Priceline provide a sort of "auction experience", a bargaining locus where pricing is strongly connected with the customer wishes. Negotiator, deal, auction as performative representations are clearly used to augment the perceived customer bargaining power.

INTUIT: CARE AND RELIABILITY IN ACCOUNTING SERVICES

Intuit is an accounting software provider for small business and accountants. Also its business model is efficiency centered as it promises to make easier and effortless the running of administration activities related to tax planning, tracking sales and expenses, paying employees.

The proposed interaction model emphasizes efficiency logic through the simplicity of the language and the narrow range of offering selection. Furthermore, the purchase process is supported and guided by free demos and on-line assistance by exploiting a chat functionality with an operator. Intuit understood a delicate issue: especially in small businesses accounting and tax planning require huge organization efforts where, instead, the attention should be placed on the core business activity. The company made a "meaning shifting" (Verganti, 2010) turning accounting into a non-specific-expertise activity and relieving companies asset and resources to manage core business issues.

The offered representation deals with a "banal" service where the different assistance gates - community, help on line, direct telephone line, free trial - promote a sense of customized caring. The deep caring aims to represent Intuit as a reliable and effective "alley" for running accounting services.

I-TUNES: A LOCKING-IN ENTERTAINMENT "VILLAGE"

I-Tunes is the virtual music Apple mall connected to the company electronic devices (I-pod, I-phone, I-Mac) where user can download and listen to the music.

Apple business model deeply exploit the lock-in source for its business model (Ostervalder, 2010) creating strong and exclusive technological ties among the music mall (I-tune), the platform hosting

the music library (pc or mac) and the device where the music and video are experienced.

As matter of fact the interaction model is designed to establish high switching costs and a widespread dominant design linked first to the brand, secondly to its products and services.

I tunes virtual mall is very easy to browse with a growing impression to enter in a sort of "entertainment village" due to the heterogeneity and content variance (streaming video, songs, concerts, audio-books, etc...).

FACEBOOK: A DAILY PRIVATE-LIFE WINDOW

Facebook is a social media where people can get in touch with friends. The massive use and its extension on a world scale have raised a lot of questions in business and financial debates.

The discussed business model, until now, is based on a lock-in system. The interactive model is based on

different kind of tools oriented to re-activate old and new relations and to maintain them with chatting and posting wall to wall and wall to many communications. Positive network effects have been reached thanks to the "avalanche effect" in coherence to the "friend of the friend" logic.

The lock-in is guaranteed thanks two main characteristics: (i) the pervasiveness of the media quickly migrated on other devices (mainly the mobile phone) and; (ii) the accumulated "capital" in terms of contacts, relations and pieces of private life (photos, communications, videos, etc...) available on the personal wall.

The performed representation, metaphorically speaking, can be depicted as "personal life window" or "dynamic friends private-life magazine" where everyone became a sort of him/her self reporter.

STUDY-CASE	BUSINESS MODEL MAIN SOURCES	INTERACTION MODEL	PERFORMED REPRESENTATIONS
Priceline	Efficiency	TASK BASED <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Search costs minimization • Speed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negotiator • Deal • Auction
Intuit	Efficiency	TASK BASED <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplicity • Narrowed selection range 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Banal" service • Alley • Caring
Apple I-Tune	Lock-In	SEARCH BASED <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Huge switching cost • Dominant design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entertainment "village"
Facebook	Lock-In	SEARCH BASED <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive Network externalities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal life windows • Friends private lifes magazines
Groupon	Novelty	DISCOVERING BASED <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New transaction structure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adverstiment wall • On sale shop windows
Amazon	Complementarities	DISCOVERING BASED <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vertical/Horizontal complementarities between products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural debate place • Generic mall

Table 1 - Table below summarizes for each study-case the business model sources, the interaction model constitutive features and the performed representations as interpreted by semiotics and interaction experts.

GROUPON: EVERYDAY A NEW DEAL!

Groupon is a internet based intermediary between discounted offers proposed by free-time, leisure and wellness operators and final end users.

Groupon business model is based on novelty as it creates a new transaction structure intermediating what before was happened in the exchanges between two single actors: producers and consumers.

This new structure assumes the form of daily announcements about the offer of the day. User receives by a every day newsletter a discounted personal offering where appears the previous price and the discounted ones, making the emphasis on

the saved money and on the time at disposal for the offering.

The performative representations for this case is connected to "advertisements wall" or an "on-sale shop window". In a more radical way it has been defined as a "democratization consumption" tool enabling also not high spending customers to access high quality offerings.

AMAZON: A REAL VIRTUAL SHOPPING MALL!

Amazon today is really different from its first steps when it entered internet as the first e-book-shop. Amazon business model is nowadays based on complementarities among different product categories. These complementarities can be vertical, where customers are tempted to buy different

products belonging to the same category (ex. books), or horizontal, where customers, because of the shipping costs, could decide to buy through different product categories (audio, books, appliances, clothes, etc.) within the same order.

The trajectory is more and more to leverage on the "one stop shopping" principle.

Interaction is supported with an internal search engine that shows the selected items and complementarily makes evident some related products (because chosen and browsed by other users searching for the same product).

The performative representations have been interpreted as "cultural debate locus", in the book area, where for each book authors' comments and tiny free reviews are available. In the other areas Amazon appears as a huge "shelf space" containing from the furniture to automotive.

CASES DISCUSSION AND LESSON LEARNT

The analysis conducted in the previous session pointed out the relation between business models and models of interaction.

As first reflection it is possible to notice that there is a clear and coherent relation in 5 of the 6 cases: Priceline, Intuit, I-Tunes, Facebook, Amazon. In these cases, indeed, interfaces and interaction models are completely designed accordingly with the business model sources. Interactions on the customers experience side act as a sort of business model mirror enabling the basic operations required to enter the business system. In different cases, according to the usability testing - as so as I-tunes or Facebook - user centered rules have not been well addressed and this has not prevent users to extensively use both services to maintain their relations or to buy, for instance, their music. This meaning that business model principles have been supported and implemented and they work well.

This choice may depend on different elements. For examples, several researchers in the last years have discussed the idea that the metrics currently used in the domain of usability studies do not work well when they are applied to measure the degree of usability for products that are more and more characterised for the emotional values they convey instead of their functionalities and efficiency.

Among them a series of contributions have explored the relationship between usability and aesthetic. In a review, Hassenzahl (2003) concluded that usability

and aesthetics correlate because of several reasons. Users may infer a higher quality of a product from its beauty that in turn implies a better usability. Norman (2005) explains has, beside the usability dimension people attraction towards products strongly depends on their capability to satisfy other class of needs related to the emotional people dimension. Costa, Rizzo and Oliva (2008) demonstrated as the interaction with Ipod is really poor with respect to the classical usability dimensions even though it has been one of the most successful interactive ever sold product. The movement beyond usability as described above has suggested that experience may depend on the sensitive condition of users and their own preferences as well as from its hedonistic characteristics: such as aesthetics, personal preferences and so on. At the same time there is no study in the field of design research that has empirically faced the measurement of the emotional dimension of usability regarding customers-company models of interaction and how they are affected by, for examples, the company brand, values, communication and other intangibles dimensions. Dealing with performative representations Priceline overturns the terms of airlines and touristic industries where companies traditionally fix prices. In Priceline user perceives to make a bid coherent to him/her value perception and paying availability. Intuit presents itself as a caring and personal accounting assistant in a sector where specialized languages and tools prevail on the real (often simple) needs of small companies. I-Tunes is not a simple database where the song query is dramatically simplified. It's the virtual place to commemorate concerts, historical band and music stars. Here the aim is to create a living and emotionally music library not a simple music e-store. Finally Groupon acts as a smart "broker" picking the best discounted offers for free-time, leisure and wellness appearing as a sort of Robin Hood releasing consumptions opportunities for low-spending customers. In any case interaction model and performative representations seem more respondent to business model principles and portrait than to the hard rules of user centred design.

These remarks disclose another perspective to intend the role of user centred study in orienting designer job. It's not in the intentions of authors to claim for the theoretical supremacy of business model principles and source on interaction design or viceversa. Our aim is to affirm that when designing new business model different design processes should be integrated and proceed in parallel. In particular we are observing that designing a business model without integrating the design competences that will define the style of interaction for a company with its end users should bring to built a huge gap between what the company is promising to its customers and the way in which this promise is communicated and made available for customers. An inclusive perspective should consider, further to the traditional UCD orienteering tools, questions and frames deriving by business models features.

FUTURE RESEARCHES

The findings discussed in this paper open new trajectories for innovative research streams, oriented to scholars and to design practitioners. The first one could be to strengthen the core of this first contribution: investigate, by exploiting a larger number of cases, the relation between business models and interaction models. Specifically, how designers assume or reflect the business models principles turning them in inputs for designing companies' interfaces and interaction models. The second stream could be represented by business model aesthetics. Designers in shaping companies interfaces build up not only the business logic but also the business portrait. Designers - more than adhering only to the UCD rules when designing users' experience- steer a middle course between brand design and business models features. In this case the analysis of the design processes should be conducted through the lenses of companies brand values and the business logic domain. The last one could investigate companies successes and failures exploiting the relation between interaction models and business models as evaluation dimension. Usually firm performances have been assessed as the result of the competitive advantage, of strategic positioning and of value proposition. The proposed stream can disclose new frames and findings where performances are determined as

function of different coupling strategies about the relation between business models and interaction patterns.

REFERENCES

- Amit R. , Zott C. (2001) Value Creation in E-business, *Strategic Management Journal*, 22.
- Brown T. (2008) *Design Thinking*, Harvard Business Review, June.
- Charles Baden-Fuller, Mary S. Morgan (2010) Business Models as Models, *Long Range Planning*, 43.
- Chesbrough H., Rosebloom R. S., The role of the business model in capturing the value from innovation, *Industrial and Corporate Change*, Vol. 11, Nr. 3, 2002
- Chesi C. Rizzo F. (2000) Open multimedia System to retrieve and organize Documents: an Adaptive Web Based IR System in the Field of textile and Clothing Industry, Adaptive Hypermedia and Adaptive web Based System. In: *Proceedings of 1st International Conference*, Springer&Verlag, Trento.
- Costa F., S. Oliva, Rizzo F. (2008) Products' Usability and Brand Preferences: the iPod Case Study. In: *Proceedings of Design Research Society Conference*, Sheffield, UK, 16-19 luglio.
- Johnson M. W., Christensen Clayton M., Kagermann H. (2008) Reinventing your business model, *Harvard Business Review*, December.
- Kolko J. (2011) *Thoughts on interaction design*, Morgan and Kauffman, USA.
- Magretta J. (2002) Why Business models Matter, *Harvard Business Review*, May.
- Mahadevan B. (2000) Business Models for Internet based E-Commerce: An Anatomy, *California Management Review*, Vol. 42, 4.
- Manzini, E., Vezzoli C. (2002) *Product-Service Systems and Sustainability: Opportunities for Sustainable Solutions*, UNEP-United Nations Environment Programme, Paris.
- Markides, C. (2006) "Disruptive Innovation: In need of a Better theory", *The Journal Product Innovation Management*, 23.
- Marti, A. H. (1999) User interface and visualization. In: R. Baeza-Yates, B. Rebeiro-Neto (Eds.), *Modern Information Retrieval*, ACM Press, Addison Wesley: New York.
- Martin R. (2009) *The Design of Business: Why Design Thinking is the Next Competitive Advantage*, Harvard Business School Press.
- Moggridge B. (2007) *Designing Interactions*, MIT press, Boston.
- Norman D. (2005) *Emotional Design*, Basic Book, New York.
- Osterwalder A., Pigneur Y. (2010) *Business Model Generation*, Wiley.
- Perkmann, M., Spicer A. (2010) What are business models? Developing a Theory of Performance Representations, *Research in the Sociology of Organization*, 29.
- Preece J., Rogers Y., Sharp H. (2011) *Interaction Design: Beyond Human - Computer Interaction*, 3rd Edition, Addison Wesley: New York.
- Rappa, M. (2001) *Managing the digital enterprise*, Business models on the Web http://ecommerce.ncsu.edu/business_models.html
- Seddon P., Lewis G. (2003) Strategy and Business Models: What's the difference? In: *Proceedings of Pacific Asia Conference on Information System - (PACIS)*.
- Shneiderman, B. (1992) *Designing the user interface: Strategies for effective human-computer interaction*, (2nd ed.), Addison

Wesley: Reading, MA.

Spink A., Saracevic T. (1998), Human computer Interaction in Information retrieval, nature and manifestation of feedback, *Interacting with Computers*, vol. 6.

Tapscott A., Lowy D. (2000) Don Ticoll, *Digital capital*, Harvard Business School Press.

Teece D. J. (2009) Business models, business strategy and innovation, *Long Range Planning* 43(2e39).

Timmers P. (1998) Business Models for Electronic Markets, *Electronic Markets*, Vol. 8, No. 2.

Tripsas M., Gavetti G., Capabilities (2000) Cognition and Inertia, *Strategic Management Journal*, 21.

Verganti R. (2010) *Design Driven Innovation*, Harvard Business Press.

Weil P., Vitale M.R. (2011) *Place to space, Migrating to e business models*, Harvard Business Press.

Yin R. K. (1994) Case Study Research. Design and Methods, Thousand Oaks, Sage, Second edition.

Zott C., Amit R., Massa L. (2010) The business model: theoretical roots, recent developments, future research, Working paper, IESE business school WP-862, June.